

ONE-STEP DWORK CONGRUENCE AND A p^{4r} -TOWER FOR SYMMETRIC-CUBE HYPERGEOMETRIC COEFFICIENTS

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ABSTRACT. Let

$$A_n := 27^n [z^n] {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3}; 1; z\right)^3, \quad B_n := (-1)^n A_n.$$

In a companion paper we proved the universal supercongruence

$$A(pm) \equiv A(m) \pmod{p^4} \quad (p \geq 5 \text{ prime}, m \geq 1)$$

and an exact all- r Fricke–Hecke vanishing statement on $X_0(3)$. In this paper we prove the one-step Dwork congruence for the symmetric-cube modular generating series

$$\Theta(t) = \sum_{n \geq 0} B_n t^n = \frac{\eta(\tau)^9}{\eta(3\tau)^3}, \quad t(\tau) = \frac{\eta(3\tau)^{12}}{\eta(\tau)^{12}},$$

namely

$$\frac{\Theta(t)}{\Theta(t^\sigma)} - \Theta_p(t) \in p^4 t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]], \quad t^\sigma = t(q^p), \quad \Theta_p(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{p-1} B_n t^n.$$

The proof uses a weight-3 modular-polynomial argument: the Hecke operator T_p on Θ^{-1} produces a modular function on $X_0(3)$ whose polynomiality in the Hauptmodul t , together with the Fricke commutation relation, forces the congruence. Combining this with the exact bridge to the Fricke–Hecke defects proved in the companion paper, we deduce the weighted coefficient statement in the variable $H(q) = q/t(q)$. Under the Dwork-type iteration of Samol–van Straten [10], this yields the full p^{4r} -tower for the coefficients A_n .

1. INTRODUCTION

Setup. Define

$$\Theta(t) := \sum_{n \geq 0} B_n t^n, \quad B_n := (-1)^n A_n, \quad A_n := 27^n [z^n] {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3}; 1; z\right)^3.$$

Let

$$(1) \quad t(\tau) := \frac{\eta(3\tau)^{12}}{\eta(\tau)^{12}} \in q \mathbf{Z}[[q]], \quad H(q) := \frac{q}{t(q)} \in 1 + q \mathbf{Z}[[q]],$$

so that $H(q) = 1 + Y(q)$ with $Y(q) = -12q + O(q^2)$. The function $t(\tau)$ is the classical Hauptmodul for $\Gamma_0(3)$; see, for example, [3, Appendix A]. Put

$$(2) \quad C(q) := \Theta(t(q)) \frac{q}{t(q)} \frac{dt}{dq} \in \mathbf{Z}[[q]],$$

a power series in q with integer coefficients.

Input from the companion paper. Throughout this paper we take as input the following four facts from the companion paper [8], each used as a black box and cited to a specific result there. The modular identification $\Theta(t(\tau)) = \eta(\tau)^9/\eta(3\tau)^3$ and the Eisenstein identification $C = 3E_{5, X_0, X_3}$ are used as inputs from [8]; the one-step proof in § 5 is otherwise self-contained.

Theorem 1.1 ([8, Thm. 3.1]). *The modular identification*

$$\Theta(t(\tau)) = \frac{\eta(\tau)^9}{\eta(3\tau)^3}$$

holds as an identity of q -series. In particular, $\Theta(t(q))$ is the q -expansion of a weight-3 η -quotient on $\Gamma_0(3)$.

Theorem 1.2 ([8, Thm. 3.1]). *With $C(q)$ as in (2),*

$$C(q) = 3E_{5,\chi_0,\chi_3}(q) = 1 + 3 \sum_{n \geq 1} \sigma_{4,\chi_3}(n)q^n,$$

where $\sigma_{4,\chi_3}(n) := \sum_{d|n} \chi_3(d)d^4$ and χ_3 is the nontrivial quadratic character modulo 3. In particular, the coefficients $c_n := [q^n]C(q)$ lie in \mathbf{Z} .

Theorem 1.3 ([8, Thm. 4.3]). *For every integer $m \geq 0$,*

$$B_m = \text{cst}_q \left(\frac{C(q)}{t(q)^m} \right) = [q^m]C(q)H(q)^m.$$

Theorem 1.4 ([8, Thm. 5.11]; all- r Fricke–Hecke vanishing, due to Beukers). *For every prime $p \geq 5$ and every integer $r \geq 1$,*

$$(3) \quad F_r(q) := \Lambda_p \left(\frac{C(q)}{t(q)^{rp}} \right) - \frac{C(q)}{t(q)^r} \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}.$$

Theorem 1.4 together with **theorem 1.3** and the identity $\text{cst}_q(\Lambda_p A) = \text{cst}_q(A)$ (valid for any Laurent series A) gives, as an immediate corollary, the one-step supercongruence

$$A(pm) \equiv A(m) \pmod{p^4} \quad (p \geq 5, m \geq 1),$$

recovering the main theorem of [8].

Main results. The Frobenius ratio is

$$(4) \quad \mu_p(t) := \frac{\Theta(t)}{\Theta(t^\sigma)}, \quad t^\sigma := t(q^p), \quad \Theta_p(t) := \sum_{n=0}^{p-1} B_n t^n.$$

Set

$$(5) \quad \Xi_p(t) := \frac{\mu_p(t) - \Theta_p(t)}{t^p} \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]],$$

and let $\tilde{\Xi}_p(Y) \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[Y]]$ be the unique series with

$$(6) \quad \tilde{\Xi}_p(Y(q)) = \Xi_p(t(q)).$$

For $N \geq 0$, define

$$(7) \quad L_N := [q^{pN}] \left(C(q)H(q)^{pN} \tilde{\Xi}_p(H(q)^p - 1) \right),$$

and also

$$(8) \quad S_N := \text{cst}_q \left(\Xi_p(t(q)) \frac{C(q)}{t(q)^N} \right).$$

Theorem 1.5 (One-step Dwork congruence). *For every prime $p \geq 5$,*

$$\mu_p(t) - \Theta_p(t) \in p^4 t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]].$$

Equivalently,

$$\Theta(t) - \Theta_p(t)\Theta(t^\sigma) \in p^4 t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]].$$

Remark 1.6 (Tower via Dwork iteration). We do not reprove the higher-step Dwork iteration here. **Theorem 1.5** is the one-step input for the Dwork-type iteration appearing in [10, Thm. 2.2]. Under that iteration one obtains, for every prime $p \geq 5$, every $r \geq 1$, and every $m \geq 1$,

$$A(p^r m) \equiv A(p^{r-1} m) \pmod{p^{4r}}.$$

Equivalently,

$$B_{p^r m} \equiv B_{p^{r-1} m} \pmod{p^{4r}}.$$

Corollary 1.7 (Weighted coefficient statement). *For every prime $p \geq 5$ and every integer $N \geq 0$,*

$$L_N \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}.$$

That is,

$$[q^{pN}] \left(C(q) H(q)^{pN} \tilde{\Xi}_p(H(q)^p - 1) \right) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}.$$

Theorem 1.8 (Equivalent forms of the one-step congruence). *For every prime $p \geq 5$, the following are equivalent:*

- (i) $\mu_p(t) - \Theta_p(t) \in p^4 t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]]$;
- (ii) $\Xi_p(t) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]]$;
- (iii) $S_N \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ for all $N \geq 0$;
- (iv) $L_N \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ for all $N \geq 0$.

All four conditions hold.

Sections 2–4 assemble the exact coefficient bridge from the companion paper and show that the weighted coefficient statement is equivalent to the one-step Dwork congruence. Section 5 supplies the missing proof of the one-step congruence by a weight-3 modular-polynomial argument. Section 6 explains why the generic unit-root bound is insufficient and how the weight-3 Hecke argument bypasses it. Section 7 records independent exact computations.

2. FINITE-DIFFERENCE CONSEQUENCES OF THE ALL- r CONGRUENCE

Throughout, Λ_p denotes the projection onto p -th coefficients, acting on Laurent series $A(q) = \sum_n a_n q^n$ by

$$(9) \quad \Lambda_p(A)(q) := \sum_n a_{pn} q^n, \quad \text{equivalently} \quad [q^N] \Lambda_p(A) = [q^{pN}] A.$$

On q -expansions of modular forms at the cusp ∞ it coincides with the Atkin U_p -operator.

We begin with an extension of [theorem 1.4](#) to the case $r = 0$. This is a weight-5 Eisenstein phenomenon already implicit in [8], but we record it explicitly here since it is needed throughout.

Lemma 2.1 (Eisenstein tower for C). *For every prime $p \geq 5$,*

$$\Lambda_p(C) - C \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}.$$

Proof. By [theorem 1.2](#), $C(q) = 1 + \sum_{n \geq 1} c_n q^n$ with

$$c_n = 3\sigma_{4,\chi_3}(n) = 3 \sum_{d|n} \chi_3(d) d^4, \quad n \geq 1.$$

Writing $n = p^j n'$ with $p \nmid n'$, multiplicativity of σ_{4,χ_3} (for $p \neq 3$) gives

$$\sigma_{4,\chi_3}(p^j n') = \left(\sum_{i=0}^j (\chi_3(p) p^4)^i \right) \sigma_{4,\chi_3}(n').$$

Hence, for any $n \geq 1$ with p -part p^j ,

$$c_{pn} - c_n = 3(\sigma_{4,\chi_3}(p^{j+1} n') - \sigma_{4,\chi_3}(p^j n')) = 3(\chi_3(p) p^4)^{j+1} \sigma_{4,\chi_3}(n').$$

In all cases $c_{pn} - c_n \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}$. For $n = 0$, $[q^0] \Lambda_p(C) = c_0 = 1 = [q^0] C$. Therefore $\Lambda_p(C) - C \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}[[q]]$. \square

Remark 2.2. The hypothesis $p \geq 5$ in [lemma 2.1](#) is stated for uniformity with the rest of the note. The coefficient identity $c_{pn} - c_n \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}$ in fact holds for every prime $p \neq 3$: the only place where $p = 3$ is excluded is in the multiplicativity formula for σ_{4,χ_3} (which requires p to be coprime to the conductor 3 of χ_3); for $p = 2$, $\chi_3(2) = -1$ and the identity becomes $c_{2n} - c_n = 3 \cdot (\chi_3(2) \cdot 2^4)^{j+1} \sigma_{4,\chi_3}(n')$, also divisible by 2^4 . The true locus of the restriction $p \geq 5$ is not here but in [proposition 3.2](#), where $1/12 \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ is needed.

It is now convenient to extend the definition of F_r to all $r \geq 0$:

$$(10) \quad F_M(q) := \Lambda_p \left(\frac{C(q)}{t(q)^{Mp}} \right) - \frac{C(q)}{t(q)^M}, \quad M \geq 0.$$

Note that $F_0(q) = \Lambda_p(C(q)) - C(q)$. Combining [theorem 1.4](#) and [lemma 2.1](#) gives:

Corollary 2.3. *For every prime $p \geq 5$ and every integer $M \geq 0$,*

$$F_M(q) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}.$$

For $N \geq 0$ define the integer-valued polynomial

$$(11) \quad P_N(X) := [q^N](C(q)H(q)^X).$$

Proposition 2.4. *For every prime $p \geq 5$, every $N \geq 0$, and every integer $m \geq 0$,*

$$(12) \quad P_{pN}(pm) \equiv P_N(m) \pmod{p^4}.$$

Moreover, writing

$$(13) \quad P_N(X) = \sum_{n=0}^N T_{N,n} \binom{X}{n}, \quad P_{pN}(pX) = \sum_{n=0}^{pN} U_{N,n} \binom{X}{n},$$

one has

$$(14) \quad U_{N,n} \equiv T_{N,n} \pmod{p^4} \quad (0 \leq n \leq N), \quad U_{N,n} \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4} \quad (n > N).$$

Proof. By [corollary 2.3](#), $F_M \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}$ for every $M \geq 0$. Since

$$\frac{C(q)}{t(q)^{Mp}} = q^{-Mp} C(q) H(q)^{Mp}, \quad \frac{C(q)}{t(q)^M} = q^{-M} C(q) H(q)^M,$$

the vanishing of F_M modulo p^4 is equivalent to

$$(15) \quad \Lambda_p(C(q)H(q)^{pM}) \equiv C(q)H(q)^M \pmod{p^4} \quad (M \geq 0).$$

Taking the coefficient of q^N in (15) with $M = m$ gives

$$[q^N] \Lambda_p(C(q)H(q)^{pm}) \equiv [q^N](C(q)H(q)^m) \pmod{p^4}.$$

Since $[q^N] \Lambda_p(A(q)) = [q^{pN}] A(q)$, this is exactly (12).

Now expand P_N and $P_{pN}(pX)$ in the Mahler basis $\binom{X}{n}$. The Mahler coefficient of $\binom{X}{n}$ in a polynomial $Q(X) \in \mathbf{Q}[X]$ is $(\Delta^n Q)(0)$, where $\Delta f(X) = f(X+1) - f(X)$. If

$$Q_N(X) := P_{pN}(pX) - P_N(X),$$

then (12) shows $Q_N(m) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ for all integers $m \geq 0$. Forward differences preserve this divisibility, so $(\Delta^n Q_N)(0) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ for every $n \geq 0$. This is precisely (14). \square

The coefficients $T_{N,n}$ are very concrete.

Lemma 2.5. *One has*

$$(16) \quad T_{N,n} = [q^N](C(q)Y(q)^n), \quad U_{N,n} = [q^{pN}](C(q)(H(q)^p - 1)^n).$$

Moreover,

$$(17) \quad T_{N,n} = 0 \quad (n > N), \quad T_{N,N} = (-12)^N.$$

In particular, $(T_{N,n})_{N,n \geq 0}$ is lower triangular with p -adically invertible diagonal for every $p \geq 5$.

Proof. Since $H(q)^X = (1 + Y(q))^X = \sum_{n \geq 0} \binom{X}{n} Y(q)^n$, the first identity in (16) follows from (11); the second is obtained similarly from $H(q)^{pX} = (H(q)^p)^X$.

Finally, $Y(q) = -12q + O(q^2)$ and $C(q) = 1 + O(q)$, so $C(q)Y(q)^n$ starts in degree n with coefficient $(-12)^n$. This gives (17). \square

3. COEFFICIENT EXTRACTION IN THE VARIABLE $Y = H - 1$

Define

$$(18) \quad S_N := \text{cst}_q \left(\Xi_p(t(q)) \frac{C(q)}{t(q)^N} \right) = [q^N] \left(C(q) H(q)^N \tilde{\Xi}_p(Y(q)) \right).$$

We first record a Lagrange–Bürmann transform which will serve as the main extraction tool.

Lemma 3.1 (Lagrange–Bürmann transform). *For every $A(q) \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$,*

$$(19) \quad \sum_{N \geq 0} t^N [q^N] (A(q) H(q)^N) = A(q(t)) \frac{t}{q(t)} \frac{dq}{dt}.$$

In particular, with $A(q) = C(q) \tilde{\Xi}_p(Y(q))$ one obtains

$$(20) \quad \sum_{N \geq 0} S_N t^N = \Theta(t) \Xi_p(t).$$

Proof. For (19), compute the coefficient of t^N on the right-hand side by a residue change of variables $q \leftrightarrow t(q)$:

$$\begin{aligned} [t^N] \left(A(q(t)) \frac{t}{q(t)} \frac{dq}{dt} \right) &= \text{Res}_{t=0} (A(q(t)) q(t)^{-1} t^{-N} dq) \\ &= \text{Res}_{q=0} (A(q) q^{-1} t(q)^{-N} dq) \\ &= [q^0] (A(q) t(q)^{-N}) \\ &= [q^N] (A(q) H(q)^N), \end{aligned}$$

where the last equality uses $t(q)^{-N} = q^{-N} H(q)^N$. The second equality is the formal residue invariance under a compositional change of variables: since $t(q) \in q\mathbf{Z}[[q]]$ with $t'(0) = 1 \neq 0$, the substitution $t \mapsto t(q)$ is a formal automorphism of $\mathbf{Q}((q))$, and formal residues at 0 are preserved under such a substitution by direct coefficient computation. Summing the resulting identity over $N \geq 0$ gives (19).

For (20), substitute $A(q) = C(q) \tilde{\Xi}_p(Y(q))$ in (19) and use

$$C(q(t)) \frac{t}{q(t)} \frac{dq}{dt} = \Theta(t), \quad \tilde{\Xi}_p(Y(q(t))) = \Xi_p(t);$$

the first of these follows from (2), which reads $C(q) = \Theta(t(q)) \cdot (q/t) \cdot (dt/dq)$, upon inversion $q \leftrightarrow t$, and the second is the definition (6). \square

Proposition 3.2. *The following are equivalent:*

- (i) $S_N \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ for all $N \geq 0$;
- (ii) $\tilde{\Xi}_p(Y) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[Y]]$;
- (iii) $\Xi_p(t) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]]$.

Hence the one-step Dwork congruence of theorem 1.5 is equivalent to the family of congruences $S_N \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$.

Proof. (i) \Leftrightarrow (iii). By lemma 3.1, $\sum_{N \geq 0} S_N t^N = \Theta(t) \Xi_p(t)$. Since $\Theta(t) = 1 + O(t) \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]]$ is a p -adic unit in the formal power series ring $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]]$, the congruence $\Theta(t) \Xi_p(t) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]]$ is equivalent to $\Xi_p(t) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]]$. Reading off coefficients gives (i) \Leftrightarrow (iii).

(ii) \Leftrightarrow (iii). From (1) and direct η -product expansion,

$$t(q) = q + 12q^2 + 90q^3 + O(q^4) \in q\mathbf{Z}[[q]];$$

in particular $t(q)$ has integer coefficients, with $[q]t = 1$ and no restriction on p needed for $t(q)$ itself. Computing the compositional inverse order by order over \mathbf{Q} gives

$$q(t) = t - 12t^2 + 198t^3 + O(t^4) \in t\mathbf{Q}[[t]],$$

and then

$$Y = \frac{q(t)}{t} - 1 = -12t + O(t^2) \in t\mathbf{Q}[[t]].$$

The obstruction to the substitution $t \leftrightarrow Y$ being a $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ -algebra automorphism of formal power series rings is precisely the denominator introduced by inverting the linear coefficient -12 of $Y(t)$. For $p \geq 5$, $1/12 \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$, so both $Y(t) \in t\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]]$ and $t(Y) \in Y\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[Y]]$, and the substitution is a $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ -algebra automorphism. (For $p = 2, 3$ this substitution fails to be integral over $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$; this is the place where the hypothesis $p \geq 5$ enters the bridge argument itself, independently of any constraint inherited from the companion inputs.) Under the identification $\Xi_p(t) = \tilde{\Xi}_p(Y)$ one has $\Xi_p \in p^4\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]] \Leftrightarrow \tilde{\Xi}_p \in p^4\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[Y]]$. \square

Remark 3.3. Substituting $\tilde{\Xi}_p(Y) = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n Y^n$ into (18) and expanding $H^N = (1 + Y)^N = \sum_k \binom{N}{k} Y^k$ gives the explicit formula

$$S_N = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n \sum_{k=0}^N \binom{N}{k} T_{N, n+k},$$

where $T_{N, m} := [q^N](C(q)Y(q)^m)$. We do not use this expansion in what follows; the proof of proposition 3.2 via lemma 3.1 and the change of variables $t \leftrightarrow Y$ is cleaner than direct coefficient matching. One should note that the simpler-looking expression $S_N = \sum_{n=0}^N a_n T_{N, n}$, which omits the H^N factor inside (18), is *false*: at $p = 5$, $N = 1$ one computes $S_1 = 31,691,250$ while $\sum_{n=0}^1 a_n T_{1, n} = 19,406,250$.

4. THE EXACT BRIDGE TO THE FRICKE–HECKE DEFECTS

Define

$$(21) \quad L_N := [q^{pN}] \left(C(q)H(q)^{pN} \tilde{\Xi}_p(H(q)^p - 1) \right).$$

By definition, the weighted coefficient condition (7) is exactly the assertion that $L_N \in p^4\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ for all N .

The point of this section is that the difference $L_N - S_N$ is controlled *exactly* by the defects (10) already shown to vanish modulo p^4 (corollary 2.3).

Proposition 4.1 (Exact defect decomposition). *For every $N \geq 0$ one has*

$$(22) \quad L_N = \text{cst}_q \Lambda_p \left(\frac{C(q)}{t(q)^{pN}} \tilde{\Xi}_p(H(q)^p - 1) \right).$$

Moreover,

$$(23) \quad L_N = S_N + \varepsilon_N,$$

where

$$(24) \quad \varepsilon_N = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n \sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^{n-j} \binom{n}{j} \text{cst}_q (q^j F_{N+j}(q)).$$

In particular,

$$(25) \quad L_N \equiv S_N \pmod{p^4} \quad (N \geq 0).$$

Proof. For (22), observe first that

$$\frac{C(q)}{t(q)^{pN}} = q^{-pN} C(q)H(q)^{pN},$$

so

$$\frac{C(q)}{t(q)^{pN}} \tilde{\Xi}_p(H(q)^p - 1) = q^{-pN} C(q)H(q)^{pN} \tilde{\Xi}_p(H(q)^p - 1).$$

Since $(H^p - 1)^n \in q^n \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$, the series $\tilde{\Xi}_p(H^p - 1)$ lies in $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$, and the Laurent series above has bounded principal part (it lives in $q^{-pN} \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$). For any Laurent series $A(q)$ with bounded principal part,

$$\text{cst}_q \Lambda_p(A) = [q^0] \Lambda_p(A) = [q^0] A = \text{cst}_q(A).$$

Applying this gives

$$\text{cst}_q \Lambda_p \left(\frac{C}{t^{pN}} \tilde{\Xi}_p(H^p - 1) \right) = [q^0] \left(\frac{C}{t^{pN}} \tilde{\Xi}_p(H^p - 1) \right) = [q^{pN}] \left(CH^{pN} \tilde{\Xi}_p(H^p - 1) \right) = L_N,$$

which is (22).

For the decomposition (23)–(24), expand

$$\tilde{\Xi}_p(H^p - 1) = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n (H^p - 1)^n = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n \sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^{n-j} \binom{n}{j} H^{pj}.$$

Since $(H^p - 1)^n \in q^n \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$, for fixed N only terms with $n \leq pN$ contribute to L_N ; thus the manipulations below produce only finitely many nonzero contributions at any fixed coefficient.

Using $CH^{pj}/t^{pN} = q^{pj} C/t^{p(N+j)}$ and $\Lambda_p(q^{pj} A) = q^j \Lambda_p(A)$ for any Laurent series A , we obtain

$$\Lambda_p \left(\frac{C}{t^{pN}} H^{pj} \right) = q^j \Lambda_p \left(\frac{C}{t^{p(N+j)}} \right) = q^j \left(\frac{C}{t^{N+j}} + F_{N+j} \right),$$

where the last equality is (10). Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_p \left(\frac{C}{t^{pN}} \tilde{\Xi}_p(H^p - 1) \right) &= \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n \sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^{n-j} \binom{n}{j} q^j \frac{C}{t^{N+j}} \\ &\quad + \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n \sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^{n-j} \binom{n}{j} q^j F_{N+j}(q). \end{aligned}$$

The first double sum simplifies to

$$\frac{C}{t^N} \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n \sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^{n-j} \binom{n}{j} \left(\frac{q}{t} \right)^j = \frac{C}{t^N} \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n (H - 1)^n = \frac{C}{t^N} \tilde{\Xi}_p(Y) = \frac{C}{t^N} \Xi_p(t(q)),$$

whose constant term in q equals S_N by (18). Taking constant terms yields (23) and (24).

We now verify that the outer sum in (24) is effectively finite, and that $\varepsilon_N \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$. Using

$$\text{cst}_q(q^j F_{N+j}(q)) = [q^{pN}] (CH^{p(N+j)}) - [q^N] (CH^{N+j}) = P_{pN}(p(N+j)) - P_N(N+j),$$

(from $F_{N+j}(q) = q^{-(N+j)} \sum_{s \geq 0} \delta_{N+j,s}(p) q^s$ with $\delta_{r,s}(p)$ as in (27) below), substitution into (24) gives

$$(26) \quad \varepsilon_N = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n \sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^{n-j} \binom{n}{j} (P_{pN}(p(N+j)) - P_N(N+j)).$$

For each fixed N , the function $X \mapsto D_N(X) := P_{pN}(pX) - P_N(X)$ is a polynomial in X of degree at most pN . The inner sum in (26) equals the n -th iterated forward difference

$$(\Delta^n D_N)(N) = \sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^{n-j} \binom{n}{j} D_N(N+j).$$

Since $\deg D_N \leq pN$, this difference vanishes for $n > pN$. Hence (26) is a finite sum over $0 \leq n \leq pN$.

By proposition 2.4, $(\Delta^n D_N)(N) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ for every $n \geq 0$: this is a restatement of (14) evaluated at the particular point $X = N$, which gives

$$D_N(N) = \sum_{k=0}^{pN} U_{N,k} \binom{N}{k} - \sum_{k=0}^N T_{N,k} \binom{N}{k},$$

and more generally $(\Delta^n D_N)(m) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ for all integers $m \geq 0$ since Δ^n of a polynomial with Mahler coefficients in $p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ evaluated on \mathbf{Z} lies again in $p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$. Since $a_n \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$, each summand in (26) lies in $p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$, and (25) follows. \square

A convenient reformulation uses the coefficients

$$(27) \quad \delta_{r,s}(p) := [q^{sp}] C(q)H(q)^{pr} - [q^s] C(q)H(q)^r.$$

Then $F_r(q) = q^{-r} \sum_{s \geq 0} \delta_{r,s}(p) q^s$, and (24) becomes

$$(28) \quad \varepsilon_N = \sum_{n=0}^{pN} a_n \sum_{j=0}^n (-1)^{n-j} \binom{n}{j} \delta_{N+j,N}(p).$$

Thus [corollary 2.3](#) controls the full error term coefficientwise.

Corollary 4.2. *For every prime $p \geq 5$, the following are equivalent:*

- (i) *the weighted coefficient condition (7);*
- (ii) $S_N \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ for all $N \geq 0$;
- (iii) $\Xi_p(t) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]]$;
- (iv) $\mu_p(t) - \Theta_p(t) \in p^4 t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]]$.

Proof. By [proposition 4.1](#), condition (i) is equivalent to $L_N \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ for all N , and this is equivalent to (ii) because $L_N \equiv S_N \pmod{p^4}$ for every N . By [proposition 3.2](#), (ii) and (iii) are equivalent. Finally, (iii) and (iv) are equivalent by the definition

$$\Xi_p(t) = \frac{\mu_p(t) - \Theta_p(t)}{t^p}.$$

\square

5. PROOF OF THE ONE-STEP DWORK CONGRUENCE

In this section we prove [theorem 1.5](#). Put

$$f(\tau) := \Theta(\tau) = \frac{\eta(\tau)^9}{\eta(3\tau)^3}, \quad g := f^{-1}.$$

Since f is a holomorphic modular form of weight 3 and character χ_3 on $\Gamma_0(3)$, the reciprocal g is a weakly holomorphic modular form of weight -3 and the same character:

$$g \in M_{-3}^!(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3).$$

For each prime $p \geq 5$, define

$$(29) \quad A_p^\sharp(q) := -\mu_p(q) - \chi_3(p) p^4 \Theta(q) U_p(\Theta^{-1})(q).$$

5.1. Exact Hecke rewrite. We use the explicit operator below; the next lemma records its q -expansion and proves that it preserves $M_k^!(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3)$ for $p \nmid 3$.

Lemma 5.1. *Let $h = \sum_{n \gg -\infty} a_n q^n \in M_k^!(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3)$ and let $p \geq 5$ be prime. Define*

$$T_p h := p^{k/2-1} \left(\sum_{b=0}^{p-1} h|_k \alpha_b + \chi_3(p) h|_k \beta \right), \quad \alpha_b = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & b \\ 0 & p \end{pmatrix}, \quad \beta = \begin{pmatrix} p & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $T_p h \in M_k^!(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3)$, and

$$(30) \quad T_p h = U_p h + \chi_3(p) p^{k-1} V_p h,$$

where $U_p(\sum a_n q^n) = \sum a_{pn} q^n$ and $V_p(\sum a_n q^n) = \sum a_n q^{pn}$.

Proof. First, (30) is a formal q -series identity. For the slash operator $(h|_k\gamma)(\tau) = (\det \gamma)^{k/2}(c\tau + d)^{-k}h(\gamma\tau)$:

$$(h|_k\alpha_b)(\tau) = p^{k/2} \cdot p^{-k} \cdot h\left(\frac{\tau+b}{p}\right) = p^{-k/2}h\left(\frac{\tau+b}{p}\right),$$

so $p^{k/2-1} \sum_{b=0}^{p-1} h|_k\alpha_b = p^{-1} \sum_{b=0}^{p-1} h\left(\frac{\tau+b}{p}\right) = U_p h$, where the last equality is the standard root-of-unity filter. Similarly, $(h|_k\beta)(\tau) = p^{k/2}h(p\tau)$, so $p^{k/2-1}\chi_3(p) h|_k\beta = \chi_3(p)p^{k-1}V_p h$. Adding yields (30).

It remains to verify the transformation law. Let

$$R_p := \{\alpha_u : 0 \leq u \leq p-1\} \cup \{\beta\}, \quad \varepsilon(\alpha_u) := 1, \quad \varepsilon(\beta) := \chi_3(p).$$

For $\gamma = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ 3c & d \end{pmatrix} \in \Gamma_0(3)$,

$$(T_p h)|_k\gamma = p^{k/2-1} \sum_{\delta \in R_p} \varepsilon(\delta) h|_k\delta\gamma.$$

For $\delta = \alpha_u$, write

$$\alpha_u\gamma = \begin{pmatrix} a+3cu & b+du \\ 3pc & pd \end{pmatrix}.$$

If $a+3cu \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, choose $u' \in \{0, \dots, p-1\}$ with $u' \equiv (b+du)(a+3cu)^{-1} \pmod{p}$. Then

$$\alpha_u\gamma = \gamma_u\alpha_{u'}, \quad \gamma_u = \begin{pmatrix} a+3cu & \frac{b+du - (a+3cu)u'}{p} \\ 3pc & d-3cu' \end{pmatrix},$$

and $\chi_3(d_{\gamma_u}) = \chi_3(d)$. If $a+3cu \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, then

$$\alpha_u\gamma = \gamma_u\beta, \quad \gamma_u = \begin{pmatrix} (a+3cu)/p & b+du \\ 3c & pd \end{pmatrix},$$

and $\chi_3(d_{\gamma_u}) = \chi_3(p)\chi_3(d)$.

For $\delta = \beta$, write

$$\beta\gamma = \begin{pmatrix} pa & pb \\ 3c & d \end{pmatrix}.$$

If $c \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, then

$$\beta\gamma = \gamma_\infty\beta, \quad \gamma_\infty = \begin{pmatrix} a & pb \\ 3c/p & d \end{pmatrix},$$

and $\chi_3(d_{\gamma_\infty}) = \chi_3(d)$. If $c \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, choose $u' \in \{0, \dots, p-1\}$ with $3cu' \equiv d \pmod{p}$. Then

$$\beta\gamma = \gamma_\infty\alpha_{u'}, \quad \gamma_\infty = \begin{pmatrix} pa & b-au' \\ 3c & (d-3cu')/p \end{pmatrix},$$

and $\chi_3(d_{\gamma_\infty}) = \chi_3(p)\chi_3(d)$.

All four displayed matrices lie in $\Gamma_0(3)$: integrality is built into the choice of u' , the lower-left entry is divisible by 3, and the determinant is $ad - 3bc = 1$. In every case

$$\delta\gamma = \gamma_\delta\delta', \quad \gamma_\delta \in \Gamma_0(3), \quad \delta' \in R_p, \quad \varepsilon(\delta)\chi_3(d_{\gamma_\delta}) = \chi_3(d)\varepsilon(\delta').$$

Applying the same construction to γ^{-1} shows that $\delta \mapsto \delta'$ is a permutation of R_p . Therefore

$$(T_p h)|_k\gamma = \chi_3(d) p^{k/2-1} \sum_{\delta' \in R_p} \varepsilon(\delta') h|_k\delta' = \chi_3(d) T_p h.$$

Thus $T_p h$ transforms with character χ_3 .

At the cusp ∞ , (30) shows that $T_p h$ has bounded principal part. At the cusp 0, with $W_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$, the matrix calculation proved below in lemma 5.3—it uses only the defining sum and the transformation law of h itself—gives

$$T_p(h|_k W_3) = \chi_3(p) (T_p h)|_k W_3.$$

Since $h|_k W_3$ has bounded principal part at ∞ , the formal identity (30) applied to the Laurent series $h|_k W_3$ shows that $T_p(h|_k W_3)$ has bounded principal part at ∞ as well. Hence $(T_p h)|_k W_3$ has bounded principal part at ∞ , so $T_p h$ is weakly holomorphic at the cusp 0. Therefore $T_p h \in M_k^!(\Gamma_0(3), \chi_3)$. \square

Applying (30) with $k = -3$ and $h = g = \Theta^{-1}$ yields

$$T_p g = U_p g + \chi_3(p) p^{-4} g(q^p).$$

Multiplying by Θ and using

$$\mu_p(q) = \frac{\Theta(q)}{\Theta(q^p)} = \Theta(q) g(q^p),$$

we obtain the exact identity

$$(31) \quad A_p^\sharp(q) = -\chi_3(p) p^4 \Theta(q) T_p(\Theta^{-1})(q).$$

Hence A_p^\sharp is a meromorphic modular function of level $\Gamma_0(3)$.

It is holomorphic on \mathfrak{H} , because η has no zeros on \mathfrak{H} , so both Θ and Θ^{-1} are holomorphic there, and the defining Hecke sum for $T_p(\Theta^{-1})$ only evaluates Θ^{-1} at points of \mathfrak{H} . It is also holomorphic at the cusp ∞ , since by definition $A_p^\sharp(q) \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$.

5.2. Fricke identity. Let

$$W_3 := \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Lemma 5.2. *One has*

$$(32) \quad \Theta|_3 W_3 = i 27 t \Theta.$$

Consequently,

$$(33) \quad \Theta^{-1}|_{-3} W_3 = -\frac{i}{27} t^{-1} \Theta^{-1}.$$

In particular,

$$(34) \quad \Theta^{-1}|_{-3} W_3 = c q^{-1} + O(1) \quad (c \neq 0),$$

and

$$(35) \quad \text{ord}_0(\Theta) = 1.$$

Proof. Using the Dedekind eta transformation law

$$\eta\left(-\frac{1}{\tau}\right) = (-i\tau)^{1/2} \eta(\tau),$$

we compute

$$\Theta\left(-\frac{1}{3\tau}\right) = \frac{\eta(-1/(3\tau))^9}{\eta(-1/\tau)^3} = i 3^{9/2} \tau^3 \frac{\eta(3\tau)^9}{\eta(\tau)^3}.$$

Therefore

$$\Theta|_3 W_3 = 3^{3/2} (3\tau)^{-3} \Theta\left(-\frac{1}{3\tau}\right) = i 27 \frac{\eta(3\tau)^{12}}{\eta(\tau)^{12}} \frac{\eta(\tau)^9}{\eta(3\tau)^3} = i 27 t \Theta,$$

which proves (32). Equation (33) follows by inversion.

Since $t(q) = q + O(q^2)$ and $\Theta(q) = 1 + O(q)$ at the cusp ∞ , equation (33) gives

$$\Theta^{-1}|_{-3} W_3 = -\frac{i}{27} q^{-1} (1 + O(q))(1 + O(q)) = c q^{-1} + O(1) \quad (c \neq 0),$$

which is (34). Finally, (32) shows that the W_3 -transform of Θ has order 1 at ∞ , hence Θ has order 1 at the cusp 0. \square

5.3. Fricke commutation.

Lemma 5.3. *For every weakly holomorphic modular form h of weight k and character χ_3 on $\Gamma_0(3)$ and every prime $p \nmid 3$,*

$$T_p(h|_k W_3) = \chi_3(p) (T_p h)|_k W_3.$$

Proof. Write

$$\alpha_b := \begin{pmatrix} 1 & b \\ 0 & p \end{pmatrix} \quad (0 \leq b \leq p-1), \quad \beta := \begin{pmatrix} p & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The double-coset formula for T_p may be written as

$$T_p h = p^{k/2-1} \left(\sum_{b=0}^{p-1} h|_k \alpha_b + \chi_3(p) h|_k \beta \right).$$

Also

$$W_3 \alpha_0 = \beta W_3, \quad W_3 \beta = \alpha_0 W_3.$$

For $1 \leq b \leq p-1$, let $b' \in \{1, \dots, p-1\}$ be defined by $3bb' \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$, and set

$$\gamma_b := \begin{pmatrix} p & -b' \\ -3b & d_b \end{pmatrix}, \quad d_b := \frac{1+3bb'}{p}.$$

Then $\gamma_b \in \Gamma_0(3)$ (indeed $\det \gamma_b = 1$), and a direct multiplication gives

$$W_3 \alpha_b = \gamma_b \alpha_{b'} W_3.$$

Since h has nebentypus χ_3 ,

$$h|_k \gamma_b = \chi_3(d_b) h.$$

Moreover $pd_b = 1+3bb' \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, so $d_b \equiv p^{-1} \equiv p \pmod{3}$, hence $\chi_3(d_b) = \chi_3(p)$. Therefore

$$h|_k W_3 \alpha_b = h|_k \gamma_b \alpha_{b'} W_3 = \chi_3(p) h|_k \alpha_{b'} W_3 \quad (1 \leq b \leq p-1).$$

As $b \mapsto b'$ permutes $\{1, \dots, p-1\}$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} T_p(h|_k W_3) &= p^{k/2-1} \left(h|_k W_3 \alpha_0 + \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} h|_k W_3 \alpha_b + \chi_3(p) h|_k W_3 \beta \right) \\ &= p^{k/2-1} \left(h|_k \beta W_3 + \chi_3(p) \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} h|_k \alpha_b W_3 + \chi_3(p) h|_k \alpha_0 W_3 \right) \\ &= \chi_3(p) p^{k/2-1} \left(\sum_{b=0}^{p-1} h|_k \alpha_b W_3 + \chi_3(p) h|_k \beta W_3 \right) \\ &= \chi_3(p) (T_p h)|_k W_3, \end{aligned}$$

since $\chi_3(p)^2 = 1$. This proves the lemma. □

5.4. Pole order at the cusp 0.

Proposition 5.4. *For every prime $p \geq 5$,*

$$\text{ord}_0(A_p^\sharp) = 1 - p.$$

Proof. Set $g := \Theta^{-1}$. By lemma 5.2,

$$g|_{-3} W_3 = cq^{-1} + O(1) \quad (c \neq 0).$$

Applying (30),

$$U_p(cq^{-1} + O(1)) = O(1), \quad V_p(cq^{-1} + O(1)) = cq^{-p} + O(1).$$

Therefore

$$T_p(g|_{-3} W_3) = \chi_3(p) p^{-4} c q^{-p} + O(1),$$

so

$$\text{ord}_\infty\left(T_p(g|_{-3}W_3)\right) = -p.$$

By the twisted commutation of lemma 5.3,

$$(T_pg)|_{-3}W_3 = \chi_3(p)^{-1}T_p(g|_{-3}W_3).$$

Since $\chi_3(p) \in \{\pm 1\}$ is a nonzero constant,

$$\text{ord}_\infty\left((T_pg)|_{-3}W_3\right) = \text{ord}_\infty\left(T_p(g|_{-3}W_3)\right) = -p,$$

and therefore

$$\text{ord}_0(T_pg) = -p.$$

Using (31) and lemma 5.2, we obtain

$$\text{ord}_0(A_p^\sharp) = \text{ord}_0(\Theta) + \text{ord}_0(T_pg) = 1 + (-p) = 1 - p.$$

□

5.5. Polynomiality and integrality.

Theorem 5.5. *For every prime $p \geq 5$, there exists a unique polynomial*

$$A_p(t) \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[t], \quad \deg A_p \leq p - 1,$$

such that

$$(36) \quad A_p(t(q)) = A_p^\sharp(q).$$

Proof. By (31), A_p^\sharp is a modular function on $X_0(3)$, holomorphic on $\mathfrak{H} \cup \{\infty\}$. By proposition 5.4, its only pole is at the cusp 0, and the pole order is at most $p - 1$.

Because $X_0(3)$ has genus 0 and t is a Hauptmodul with a simple zero at ∞ and a simple pole at 0, every such modular function is a polynomial in t of degree at most $p - 1$. Thus there is a unique polynomial

$$A_p(t) \in \mathbf{C}[t], \quad \deg A_p \leq p - 1,$$

satisfying (36).

Since $A_p^\sharp(q) \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$ and $t(q) = q + 12q^2 + \dots$, the substitution map

$$\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[t]_{\leq p-1} \hookrightarrow \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$$

is triangular with unit diagonal. Therefore the coefficients of $A_p(t)$ lie in $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$. □

5.6. Completion of the proof.

Proof of theorem 1.5. By (29) and theorem 5.5,

$$(37) \quad A_p(t) + \mu_p(t) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]].$$

On the other hand,

$$(38) \quad t^\sigma = t(q^p) = t^p + O(t^{p+1}),$$

so the first p Taylor coefficients of $\mu_p(t)$ agree with those of $\Theta(t)$, and hence

$$(39) \quad \mu_p(t) - \Theta_p(t) \in t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]].$$

Set

$$R_p(t) := A_p(t) + \Theta_p(t).$$

Then $\deg R_p \leq p - 1$, and subtracting (39) from (37) gives

$$R_p(t) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]] + t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]].$$

Because R_p has degree at most $p - 1$, every coefficient of R_p is determined modulo t^p ; therefore every coefficient is divisible by p^4 , i.e.

$$R_p(t) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[t].$$

It follows that

$$\mu_p(t) - \Theta_p(t) = (\mu_p(t) + A_p(t)) - (A_p(t) + \Theta_p(t)) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]].$$

Combining this with (39), we obtain

$$\mu_p(t) - \Theta_p(t) \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]] \cap t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]] = p^4 t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]],$$

which is the asserted one-step Dwork congruence. \square

Proof of corollary 1.7. This is immediate from theorems 1.5 and 1.8. \square

On remark 1.6. This paper proves the one-step congruence of theorem 1.5. The passage from that one-step congruence to the higher-step tower is the Dwork-type iteration cited in remark 1.6; we do not reprove it here.

6. WHY THE GENERIC UNIT-ROOT BOUND IS INSUFFICIENT AND HOW THE MODULAR POLYNOMIAL BYPASSES IT

The proof of theorem 1.5 does not come from a blanket improvement of generic unit-root precision. Rather, it combines two ingredients of different origins: the weight-5 Fricke–Hecke vanishing from the companion paper and the weight-3 modular-polynomial argument of § 5.

Generic unit-root precision. The underlying motive is naturally the symmetric cube of an elliptic object, and the expected unit-root F -crystal has slopes $\{0, 3\}$ before the weight-5 Kodaira–Spencer correction. The heuristic of Rodriguez Villegas on Hodge decompositions of the associated motive [7], together with the foundational unit-root theory of Katz [5], suggests generic precision p^{k-1} for weight k . In the present setting this predicts p^3 , not p^4 .

Thus the one-step Dwork congruence is invisible to generic unit-root bounds alone.

The companion gain and the exact bridge. The all- r Fricke–Hecke vanishing of theorem 1.4 is a genuine weight-5 phenomenon going beyond the generic bound. Sections 2–4 show that this gain controls the difference between the weighted coefficients L_N and the extraction coefficients S_N exactly: for every N , the error term is a finite linear combination of forward differences of the Mahler defect polynomial, and each such difference lies in $p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$ by proposition 2.4.

By itself, however, that bridge does not prove the one-step congruence. What remains is to show that the modular function arising from the coefficient of the weight-3 modular polynomial is itself a polynomial in the Hauptmodul t of degree at most $p - 1$. That is precisely the role of § 5: the Hecke rewrite (31), the exact Fricke identity (32), and the commutation relation with W_3 force the required pole bound at the cusp 0, and genus 0 then turns the modular function into a polynomial in t .

In this way the extra p -adic digit is produced by a weight-3 modular-polynomial argument rather than by a stronger generic unit-root estimate.

Relation to the Beukers–Vlasenko framework. The general framework of Beukers–Vlasenko [2] formulates, for suitable Calabi–Yau families, a conjectural link between Hasse–Witt conditions and p^{ks} -tower congruences. Their [2, Conj. 7.5] remains open in general. The symmetric-cube hypergeometric setting ${}_2F_1(1/3, 1/3; 1; z)^3$ considered here is not one of the geometric families covered by that conjecture. Nevertheless, the present argument closes the corresponding $\text{Sym}^3/X_0(3)$ case by a direct modular-form method: the weight-5 Fricke–Hecke vanishing gives the exact coefficient bridge, and the weight-3 Hecke argument proves the one-step congruence itself without appealing to the full crystalline formalism.

7. COMPUTATIONAL VERIFICATION

The computations in this section are independent checks of the theorems proved above. All calculations were carried out in exact arithmetic over \mathbf{Q} via η -product expansions of $t(q)$, $H(q)$, and $\Theta(t(q))$, with coefficient precision q^M chosen large enough for the required range. Independent reproductions via the hypergeometric formula for A_n give identical values of $B_n = (-1)^n A_n$ in the overlapping range.

Consistency of the companion inputs.

- (a) *Eisenstein identity.* For $n \leq 40$, $[q^n]C(q) = 3\sigma_{4,\chi_3}(n)$ for $n \geq 1$ and $[q^0]C(q) = 1$, in agreement with [theorem 1.2](#).
- (b) *Eisenstein tower.* $v_p([q^n]\Lambda_p C - [q^n]C) \geq 4$ for all tested n and $p \in \{5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29, 31\}$, in agreement with [lemma 2.1](#).
- (c) *All- r vanishing.* $F_r(q) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^4}$ for $0 \leq r \leq 4$ and $p \leq 19$ in the tested coefficient range, in agreement with [corollary 2.3](#).

Independent checks of the one-step congruence.

- (1) For every tested prime $p \in \{5, 7, 11, 13, 17\}$, the coefficients of

$$\mu_p(t) - \Theta_p(t)$$

through degree t^{20} are divisible by p^4 , with equality at p^4 occurring in the first nonzero range.

- (2) For every tested pair (p, N) with $p \in \{5, 7, 11, 13\}$ and $0 \leq N \leq 20$, the weighted coefficients satisfy

$$L_N \in p^4 \mathbf{Z}_{(p)},$$

in agreement with [corollary 1.7](#).

- (3) As an independent check of [proposition 4.1](#), both L_N and S_N were computed separately and found to satisfy

$$v_p(L_N - S_N) \geq 4$$

in the tested range.

Exact modular-polynomial coefficients. The polynomiality statement of [theorem 5.5](#) can be seen explicitly in low primes. For $p = 5, 7, 11$ the exact polynomials $A_p(t)$ are:

$$A_5(t) = 624 + 2238759t + 406552365t^2 + 19758444939t^3 + 282429536481t^4,$$

$$A_7(t) = -2402 - 85463586t - 55995812406t^2 - 9073000431891t^3 \\ - 571919811374025t^4 - 15441834907098675t^5 - 150094635296999121t^6,$$

$$A_{11}(t) = 14640 + 26714715300t + 131585427203436t^2 + 111863014828359066t^3 \\ + 34290167120086502286t^4 + 5037468737757129091638t^5 \\ + 404379262821033745831602t^6 + 18738111307760623026900459t^7 \\ + 500374897421221254372863553t^8 + 7152417651373927341917990787t^9 \\ + 42391158275216203514294433201t^{10}.$$

In each case the t -expansion truncates exactly at degree $p - 1$, as predicted by [theorem 5.5](#).

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